

The Influence of Information Literacy Skill on LIS Students' Use of Online Information Resources in Some Selected Universities in the South-South, Nigeria

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Abstract

The study aims to determine how undergraduate students identify the needed information, locate and use online information resources, and evaluate and use online information resources. A questionnaire was used to collect data from 521 library and information science students in four universities in the south-south of Nigeria. The study revealed that the majority of the LIS students agreed that they needed information to write their course assignments, to prepare for their class discussions, to write their seminar papers, and to write their final year research papers. The study also found that the LIS students use online information resources such as e-journals, the internet, online databases, and search engines, while they indicated not using e-theses and dissertations, and Online Public Access Catalogue. This might be due to a lack of awareness and skills to use these online resources. The study also revealed that most LIS students consider well-known author(s), the currency of the information resource, the credibility of the information, the accuracy of the information, and the relevance of the information resource when evaluating online information resources. Therefore, the findings call for university libraries to evaluate the effectiveness of the library orientation, user education and information literacy programmes offered to students.

Keywords: Information resources, information literacy (IL), academic libraries, online information resources, library and information science, undergraduate students.

Introduction

Information literacy is becoming increasingly important in our world, and it is rapidly evolving due to the growth and proliferation of technological and information resources (Nierenberg, 2016). As a result, information users are faced with countless information choices and must decide which resource(s) to use in the acquisition of information. They also determine the authenticity, validity and usability of the information they discover (Nierenberg, 2016). The ability to access, evaluate and use information is a prerequisite for lifelong learning and a basic requirement for the information society. Ojedokun and Lumade (2005) describe information literacy as the ability to locate, evaluate, manage and use information from various sources for problem-solving, decision-making and research. Information literacy is much broader than the acquisition of traditional information skills. This includes how to use a catalogue, locate a book on the shelves and access an electronic database.

Julien (2002) believes that an information-literate person today should possess specific online searching skills such as the ability to select appropriate search terminology, logical search strategy and appropriate information evaluation. However, one barrier to the efficient utilization of information resources, especially electronic resources, in developing countries is the relatively low level of information literacy skill (Julien, 2002; Tilvawala, Myers & Andrade, 2009). Users of information resources must possess information literacy skills to harness information resources at their disposal. To respond effectively to an ever-changing

environment, users of information resources need more than just a knowledge base; they also need techniques for exploring it, which will connect it to other knowledge bases and thus make practical use of it for rational decision-making or problem-solving. In other words, the landscape upon which we stand has been transformed, and users of information resources are being forced to establish a new foundation called information literacy (Owusu-Ansah, 2004). It is important to understand that availability and access to information are insufficient to guarantee that a library user will acquire the skills necessary to survive in an information world comfortably. According to the Association of College & Research Libraries (2005), information literacy is a set of abilities requiring individuals to recognize when information is needed and have the ability to locate, evaluate, and use effectively the needed information. Information literacy is focused on content, communication, analysis, information searching, and evaluation.

Nowadays, the prevalence of information and communication technologies “in every possible setting” means that information literacy remains an essential skill for all (Eisenberg, 2008) and a requirement for “full participation in contemporary societies” (Julien & Backer, 2009, p.7). Information literacy skills (ILs), according to Parang, Raine and Stevenson (2000), is a fusion of library literacy, computer literacy, media literacy, technological literacy, critical thinking, ethics and communication, which, when acquired, would enable users of information to become independent lifelong learners. ILs enable individuals to recognize when information is needed and when different kinds of information are needed. It provides users of information resources with methods by which they can cope with the huge quantity of information coming from all directions through all varieties of information resources. It can then be assumed that information literacy skills are needed by undergraduate students for effective use of information resources for quantity and quality research output.

Nierenberg (2016) argued that the information age and its far-reaching technological developments have changed the ways in which users relate to and use information, making information literacy skills an essential set of skills and competencies that impact the daily lives of individuals living in an information society. Navigating through the plethora of information stored on the Internet to find accurate and reliable information will be a new form of literacy called “online information literacy skills” (Eke, Omekwu & Agbo, 2014). Information literacy skills among undergraduate students in universities will help them to understand issues of plagiarism, good academic writing, achieve good academic grades, and achieve clarity in presentation of ideas in writing class assignments, evaluating and citing online information sources (Nierenberg, 2016). It requires one to recognize and use that power, to manipulate and transform digital media, to distribute pervasively, and to easily adapt them to new forms (Becker, 2018). A person with information literacy skills is deemed to have various cognitive and technical skills to find, understand, evaluate, create, and communicate digital information in various formats (ALA, 2013, p.1). With information literacy skills, students are able to search for relevant information among the unorganized sources of information on the internet, easily navigate through different websites, evaluate the credibility of the information on websites, and communicate with people from many different countries with different cultures (Becker, 2018). The essence of it all is that a 21st-century information user should possess information literacy skills, which will enable them to effectively construct search terms and critically evaluate information sources retrieved online, among other aspects, to deal with the problems of information overload.

Electronic resources (ERs) are changing the pattern of library information and services provision as seen from the recent pattern of acquisition, organization and dissemination of information (Daramola, 2016). ERs, in the context of this work, refer to all the information

materials in the library that can only be accessed electronically using Information Communication Technology (ICT) facilities. These resources include all electronic collections in e-books, CD-ROM databases, online databases, e-journals, online public access catalogues (OPACs), Internet resources, multi-media resources, etc. These resources are established by the existing body of literature to be relevant to students in their academic and life-long learning. As a result, ERs are an important element for the academic community as they enable users to access up-to-date information in the right format without spending much time. However, it is also worth noting that the benefits that institutions reap from investments in information technologies and ERs are influenced by the extent to which users possess the required information literacy skills necessary for utilizing them. As part of orienting students to the library and information resources, university libraries conduct library orientation and user education programmes. The programme aims to familiarise students with the use of the library and information resources, especially on how they can easily locate information resources online and on the shelves. The researcher observed that students are not oriented on how to search and access online information resources despite all the effort provided in the libraries. Some studies have shown that undergraduate students find it difficult to effectively locate information resources and lack the ability to evaluate online information resources (Keboh & Baro, 2020). Therefore, this study aims to investigate the impact of information literacy skills on Library and Information Science (LIS) students' use of online information resources in some selected universities in the south-south of Nigeria.

Research questions

- RQ1. How do the LIS undergraduate students identify the needed information?
- RQ2. What are the online information resources used by the LIS undergraduate students?
- RQ3. How do LIS undergraduate students' ability to locate information influence their use of online resources?
- RQ4. How does a student's ability to evaluate information influence their use of online information resources?

Literature review

Undergraduate students need for online information

The growth of electronic information resources has become a global phenomenon, especially in developed societies, due to technological advancement in information technology (IT). As the volumes of electronic information are constantly increasing, search skills are required in order to gain access to the information that is available. Undergraduates in academic environments should be able to recognise information needed for learning and research, distinguish ways of addressing gaps and locate information stored in electronic resources. To gain access to and use these vast resources effectively, information users must learn to overcome information anxiety and explore the available information to enable them to interpret and utilize information for academic use. ERs play prominent roles in facilitating access to needed information easily and speedily. Ukachi (2015) stated that the goal of ERs is to ensure that the needed information is provided to the user at the right time. ERs can be used by any user through online access via networks or authentication methods at any time by comfortably sitting at home or in an office. This access aids users in keeping abreast with current developments in their respective subject fields, distinct from print media which are not regularly updated like the electronic ones. However, it is vital that one should be conversant with the use and exploitation of ERs by being information literate in order to achieve quicker and more effective usage.

It is imperative to note that many students use library e-resources to accomplish their course work, research papers, thesis, and dissertation (Jabeen & Imran, 2017). Khan and Sheikh

(2014) discovered that students use the resources offered in various electronic formats to complete their classwork and assignments, activities, and exam preparation. Sife (2014) explains that there is a growing reliance among students on web-based information resources for educational purposes and the use of online information for personal spaces. Many undergraduate students frequently use online information for research, and class assignments to supplement lecturer notes (Chawinga & Zozie, 2016; Lwehabura, 2016).

Online information resources used by undergraduate students

The resources provided by university libraries come either in printed or electronic formats. ERs are an inseparable part of today's educational system. Saye (2001) defined electronic information resources (EIRs) as those that are generated through some electronic medium and made available to a wide range of viewers on-site and off-site via some electronic transferring machine or the Internet. Studies have shown that undergraduate students use electronic information resources such as databases, online databases, online journals, OPACs, the Internet, and other computer-based electronic networks (Lwehabura, 2016; Ukachi, 's 2015). Ukachi's (2015) study asked respondents about the various electronic resources provided in their university libraries. The study found that the available ERs in their libraries are e-journals, e-books, OPACs, online databases and Internet resources. Ankrah and Acheampong (2017) studied students' use of electronic resources at the University of Professional Studies, Accra, Ghana. The study revealed the different types of e-resources available and used by the UPSA Library students. They are Emerald, Wiley Online Library, Sage Journals Online, EBSCOhost, JSTOR, Oxford University Press, Policy Press Journals, Taylor and Francis, and IMF e-Library.

Ekenna and Iyabo (2013) observed that students' efforts to complement their work with e-resources may be limited due to a lack of locating needed information resources. Therefore, knowledge of where to locate needed information resources is necessary to selectively locate accurate, relevant and up-to-date information stored in documents instead of all the information that may not be relevant to their academic work. In Africa, information searching and retrieval are particularly challenging for university students (Chawinga & Zozie, 2016; Lwehabura, 2016). Adeniran (2018) investigated the influence of information literacy skills and computer self-efficacy on postgraduate students' use of e-resources in private university libraries in Nigeria. The study revealed a significant positive correlation between information literacy skills and the use of e-resources. The study concluded that using e-resources promoted access to current information among postgraduate students in the selected private universities in Nigeria.

Students' ability to evaluate online information and Resources.

Information evaluation systematically determines the merit and worth of information (Belanger et al., 2019). As the internet is flawed and has information quality problems, students need to have the ability to discern between good and bad information and decide on using the most relevant information for their tasks. This search for quality information is found via academic databases, which play significant roles in scholarship all over the globe (Irenoa & Sawyerr-George, 2022). Helping undergraduates locate, identify, evaluate, and use information is a concern of both librarians and faculty. Okeji, Ilika and Baro (2020) assessed the information literacy skills of final-year undergraduates in library and information science at Nigerian universities. One of the purposes of the study was to determine the extent to which the undergraduates of LIS evaluate online information. The undergraduate students rated well-known author(s), current information, credible information, and accurate and relevant information as important when evaluating online information resources.

The study by Currie et al. (2010) asked undergraduates how they determined whether a source was scholarly. A variety of statements were expressed in response to this question. The authors reported that two students were looking for peer-reviewed articles. Four students noted the existence and value of references and cited sources. Several students commented on the prestige of the journal that published the article, and four believed that searching in a scholarly database leads to scholarly literature. Dreisiebner and Schlogl (2019) found, among others, that the critical evaluation of sources is addressed in all disciplines but relates to different contexts. The study by Elswailer and Kattenbeck (2019) on “understanding credibility judgments for web search snippets” revealed that users were very uncertain when assessing credibility, and their impressions often diverged from objective judges who have checked the sources. The most notable finding was not how decisions were based but rather how inaccurate and uncertain participants were in their judgments.

Methodology

The study employed a descriptive survey method. It is a survey research aimed at determining undergraduate students' information literacy and the use of online information resources in university libraries. The study population consist of all questionnaire library and information science students in some selected universities in the south-south of Nigeria. The universities are Niger Delta University, Amassoma, Ignatius Ajuru University of Education, Port Harcourt, Delta State University, Abraka. and Rivers State University of Science and Technology, Port Harcourt. The instrument used for data collection was a questionnaire. The questionnaire is titled Information Literacy and Use of Online Information Resources (ILUOIR). The researcher, together with research assistants, visited the library and information science department of the four universities and distributed copies of the questionnaire to the students in their various classes. A convenient sampling technique was used to select 570 respondents for the 2023-2024 academic session. Of the 570 copies of the questionnaire distributed to the respondents in their respective classrooms, 521 completed and returned copies were used for analysis. Data collected was analyzed using a simple percentage method to answer the four research questions. For clarity, the results are presented in tables.

Results

Table 1: Universities, population and sample size of respondents

Universities	Population	Sample	Response rate
Ignatius Ajuru	278	154	55.4%
RSUST	195	98	50.3%
Delsu	330	144	43.6%
NDU	214	125	58.4%
Total	1,017	521	51.2%

Results in Table 1 shows the universities, population and sample size of the respondents. In total, 521 respondents responded to the study with response rate of 51.2%.

Table 2: Respondents' level of study.

Universities	100L	200L	300L	400L	Total
Ignatius Ajuru Uni.	56	37	39	22	154
RSUST	39	32	15	12	98
Delsu	48	51	27	18	144
NDU	21	42	57	5	125
Total	164	162	138	57	521

Out of the 521 respondents, 164(31.5%) indicated as 100 level, 162 (31.1%) indicated as 200 level students, 138 (26.5%) indicated as 300 level students, and 57(10.9%) indicated as 400 level students.

How do the LIS students identify the needed information?

Table 3: Students' identification of needed information.

Ability to identify needed information	Strongly Agree	Agree	Disagree	Strongly Disagree
I need sport information	55 (10.6%)	38 (7.3%)	306 (58.7%)	122 (23.4%)
I need health information	101(19.4%)	98(18.8%)	263(50.5%)	59(11.3%)
I need information to write any course assignment	240(46.1%)	269(51.6%)	12(2.3%)	-(0.0%)
I need information to prepare for my class discussion	279(53.6%)	242(46.4%)	-(0.0%)	-(0.0%)
I need information to write my seminar papers	310(59.5%)	202(38.8%)	9(1.7%)	-(0.0%)
I need information to write my final year research paper	408(78.3%)	113(21.7%)	-(0.0%)	-(0.0%)

The majority (428: 82.1%) of the respondents disagree and strongly disagree that they need sports information. The majority (322: 61.8%) of the respondents disagree and strongly disagree that they need health information. The majority (509: 97.7%) of the respondents strongly agree that they need information to write their course assignments. All (521: 100%) of the respondents strongly agree that they need information to prepare for their class discussions. Almost all (512: (68.7%) of the respondents strongly agree that they need information to write their seminar papers. Most respondents (521: 100%) strongly agree that they need information to write their final year research paper.

What are the online information resources used by undergraduate students?

Table 4: Online information resources students consult

S/n	Online information resources	Used	Not used
1	Ebooks	128 (24.6%)	393(75.4%)
2	E-journals	498 (95.6%)	23(4.4%)
3	Internet	521(100%)	-
4	Online Databases	482 (92.5%)	39(7.5%)
5	Online Public Access Catalogue	477 (91.6%)	44 (8.4%)
6	E – theses and dissertations	12 (2.3%)	509 (97.7%)

7	Search engines	432 (82.9%)	89 (17.1%)
8	Websites	412 (79.1%)	109 (20.9%)

Most respondents (393: 75.4%) indicated that they did not use e-books. Almost all (498: 95.6%) respondents indicated that they used E-journals. All (521: 100%) of the respondents indicated using the internet. Almost all (482: 92.5%) respondents used the online database. The majority (477: 91.6%) of the respondents indicated that they did not use the Online Public Access Catalogue. Almost all (509: 97.7%) respondents indicated not using E-theses and dissertations. Most respondents (432: 82.9%) indicated using search engines. Most respondents (412: 79.1%) indicated that they were using websites.

How do LIS students' ability to locate information influence their use of online information?

Table 5: Students' ability to locate information from online information resources.

Ability to locate information from e-resources	Very poor	Poor	Average	Good	Very good
My ability to locate information from E – book is	194 (37.2%)	127 (24.4%)	150 (98.7%)	40 (7.7%)	10 (1.9%)
My ability to locate information from E-journal is	2 (0.4%)	12 (2.3%)	96 (18.4%)	302 (58.0%)	109 (20.9%)
My ability to locate information on the Internet is	-	-	56 (10.7%)	267 (51.2%)	198 (38.0%)
My ability to locate information from online databases is	4 (0.8%)	1 (0.2%)	212 (40.7%)	104 (20.0%)	200 (38.4%)
My ability to locate information from the Online Public Access Catalogue is	19 (3.6%)	28 (5.4%)	188 (36.1%)	198 (38.0%)	172 (33.0%)
My ability to locate information from E-theses and dissertations is	235 (45.1%)	162 (31.1%)	110 (21.1%)	5 (1.0%)	9 (1.7%)

Regarding locating information from e-books, the majority (150: 98.7%) rated their ability to be average, followed by (194: 37.2%) respondent who rated their ability to be very poor. The majority (302: 58.0%) of the respondent rated their ability to locate information from e-journals as good. The majority (267: 51.2%) of the respondents rated their ability to locate information from the Internet as good (109: 20.9%). Most respondents (212: 40.7%) rated their ability to locate information from online databases as average and very good (200: 38.4%). The majority (198: 38.0%) of the respondents rated their ability to locate information from the Online Public Access Catalogue as good and average (188: 36.1%). On their ability to locate information from e-theses and dissertations, the majority (235: 45.1%) rated their ability to be very poor and poor (162: 31.1%).

To what extent do LIS students evaluate online information for academic use?

Table 6: Students evaluation of online information for academic use.

Factors to consider when evaluating online information	SA	A	D	SD
I consider well-known author(s) before using any material	301 (57.8%)	159 (30.5%)	47 (9.0%)	14 (2.7%)
I look at how current the information resource is	288 (55.3%)	172 (33.0%)	48 (9.2%)	13 (2.5%)
I consider the credibility of the information before use	179 (34.4%)	213 (40.8%)	91 (17.5%)	38 (7.3%)
I consider the accuracy of information before the use	204 (39.2%)	248 (47.5%)	27 (5.2%)	42 (8.1%)
I consider the relevance of information resources before use	328 (63.0%)	188 (36.0%)	5 1.0	- (0.0%)

Most respondents (460: 88.3%) strongly agree that they consider well-known author(s) before using any material. The majority (460: 88.3%) of the respondents agree and strongly agree to look at the current information resources. The majority (392: 75.2%) of the respondents strongly agree and agree to consider the credibility of the information before use. The majority (452: 86.7%) of the respondents agree and strongly agree that they consider the accuracy of the information before use. Almost all (516: 99%) of the respondents strongly agree that they consider the relevance of information resources before use.

Discussion of findings

LIS students identify the needed information

The study revealed that most LIS students strongly agreed and agreed that they needed information to write their course assignments, prepare for their class discussions, write their seminar papers, and write their final year research papers. Many undergraduate students frequently use online information for research and class assignments to supplement lecturer notes. This finding agrees with the literature as several authors have reported that a great number of students use library e-resources to accomplish their course work, research papers, thesis, and dissertation (Jabeen & Imran, 2017; Khan & Sheikh, 2014; Chawinga & Zozie, 2016; Lwehabura, 2016). For example, Khan and Sheikh (2014) discovered that students use a huge number of resources offered in various electronic formats to complete their classwork and assignments activities and exam preparation.

The online information resources used by undergraduate students

Findings from the study revealed that most LIS students use the following online information resources: e-journals, the internet, online databases, and search engines, but they indicated not using e-theses and dissertations and the Online Public Access Catalogue. This finding supports earlier findings in the literature where studies reported undergraduates' reliance on and use of electronic information resources in universities (Dadzie, 2015; Ukachi, 's 2015). For example, Dadzie (2015) investigated the use of electronic resources by students and faculty of Ashesi University in Ghana to determine the level of use, the type of information accessed and the effectiveness of the library's communication tools for information research and problems faced in using electronic resources. Her findings revealed that almost 85 per cent of the respondents used the internet to access information. Similarly, Ansari and Zuberi (2010) conducted similar research at the University of Karachi and found that electronic resources were widely used in the universities.

On a contrary note, the study revealed that undergraduate students are not using e-theses, dissertations, and the Online Public Access Catalogue. This finding agrees with the findings of

Daramola (2016), who established that the use of electronic resources, especially among undergraduates, is not as high as expected. The implication of the low use is that the undergraduates will not be able to carry out research that requires current and up-to-date literature, which may diminish the potential, considering the enormous investment in electronic resources. The reason for undergraduate students in this study not using electronic resources like E-theses and dissertations might be due to a lack of awareness of the existence of E-theses and dissertations. Therefore, this calls for an awareness campaign to educate undergraduate students about the availability of e-theses and dissertations and the need to use them for academic purposes.

LIS students' ability to locate information influences their use of online information.

On how undergraduate students' ability to locate information influences their use of online information, the study revealed that the majority rated their ability to locate e-journals as very good, Online Public Access Catalogue as average, and Internet and Online Database as good. This shows that LIS undergraduate students can locate and use some electronic resources, which is very good. Aduba, Obot, and Baro (2022) compared Information literacy skills among Students of Library and Information Science and Computer Science in Nigerian Universities and found that the students from LIS are more information literate than their CS counterparts. The reason for the difference was that at the LIS department in UNIZIK, the information literacy course is being taught as a standalone course in the curriculum, while it is not so in the CS department. This gives LIS students the advantage of acquiring skills to locate and retrieve different online resources. The majority rated their ability to locate e-books, e-theses, and dissertations as poor or very poor. The inability to locate e-theses and dissertations might be due to their lack of skills and awareness of the availability of theses and dissertations in the various university libraries. This calls for intensifying the library use education programme and training of users on these online resources. This finding aligns with several studies' findings that information searching and retrieval is a challenging task for university students (Chawinga & Zozie, 2016; Lwehabura, 2016). For example, Lwehabura (2016) reported that students experienced challenges locating information from the Online Public Access Catalogue (OPAC), searching and retrieving academic information from the Internet, using online databases and evaluating information from the Internet. Similarly, Ekenna and Iyabo (2013) studied information retrieval skills and university undergraduates' use of electronic library resources in Nigeria. They found that Informational, operational, and strategic retrieval skills correlated significantly with students' utilization of electronic resources for research. The data showed that undergraduates lacked the requisite skills to use e-resources.

The extent to which LIS students evaluate online information for academic use

Regarding the extent to which LIS students evaluate online information for academic use revealed that the majority of the respondents strongly agree and agree that they consider well-known author(s), look at the currency of the information resources, the credibility of the information, the accuracy of the information, and relevance of information resource. This finding confirms the findings of Okeji, Ilika and Baro (2020), who, in their study, assessed final-year undergraduates of LIS in 15 universities in Nigeria and found that the undergraduates rated well-known author(s), current information, credible information, accurate and relevant information as very important when evaluating online information resources. Evaluating the authority means looking critically at the information's author and the sponsor or owner of the specific resource. Your goal is to determine if those who wrote the information are qualified to do so and whether they are providing credible information.

From the analysis, information currency was rated as very important by a majority of the undergraduates. Currency refers to the timeliness of the information. The currency of a print

product is determined by the date of publication. An information-literate student also understands how current the information has to be for a specific purpose. The findings confirm the view by Kuhlthau (2012) that judging usefulness means looking at the quality, expertise, accuracy, currency and perspective, determining importance and relevance. With the tremendous amount of information available today, information evaluation has become an important skill. As an undergraduate, you need to be able to sift through and evaluate many kinds of information. Knowing how to evaluate the information you must deal with is particularly important. Information evaluation systematically determines the merit and worth of information (Belanger et al., 2019). The study by Elswailer and Kattenbeck (2019) on “understanding credibility judgments for web search snippets” revealed that users were very uncertain when assessing credibility. Their impressions often diverged from objective judges who have checked the sources. The most notable finding was not how decisions were based but rather how inaccurate and uncertain participants were in their judgments. According to Elswailer and Kattenbeck (2019), teaching undergraduates how to evaluate Web pages critically involves not only assessing aspects of authority, accuracy, objectivity, currency and coverage but also doing so in an analytical fashion, promoting peer-reviewed and editorially-reviewed resources, as well as using further sources to compare and corroborate contained facts

Conclusion

From the analysis, it could be concluded that the LIS undergraduate students in the selected universities needed information to write their course assignments, prepare for their class discussions, write their seminar papers, and write their final year research papers. It also emerged that undergraduate Library and Information Science students use online information resources such as e-journals, the internet, Online databases, and search engines. In contrast, they do not use E-theses, dissertations, and e-books. The undergraduate students rated their ability to locate the E-journal, the Internet, and the Online Database as good. The undergraduate students of Library and Information Science of the four universities considered well-known author(s) look at the current information resources, the credibility of the information, the accuracy of the information, the relevance of information resource, and the information retrieved to be free from bias before using any material.

Recommendations

1. An aggressive awareness campaign must be carried out to raise awareness of the availability of various online information resources, such as e-theses, dissertations, and databases. The awareness campaign on electronic resources should start during library orientation and be an ongoing process. Awareness can still be created during the “Use of Library” course for all fresh students.
2. The universities in Nigeria should intensify their efforts in information literacy, adequate training in using electronic sources, and skills development.

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